

ES Observer Role Training and Resources Manual (2023–2024)

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This training and resources document compiles the guidance provided to ES Observers through the Eclipse Soundscapes website, live and recorded training webinars, and time-relevant email reminders. It also documents key participation structures, accessibility considerations, and implementation decisions that shaped the ES Observer role during the 2023 and 2024 eclipse periods.

The document reflects the information made publicly available to participants, along with contextual details preserved here for reference, transparency, and long-term reuse. This archived compilation reflects the ES Observer role as implemented during the 2023 annular and 2024 total solar eclipses and is preserved as a historical and methodological record of participant guidance during those eclipse events. Following the 2023 annular eclipse, structured role-specific email communication was implemented to reduce confusion and provide just-in-time guidance prior to the 2024 total solar eclipse.

Observer Role Overview

Intended Audience: Volunteer scientists participating in the Eclipse Soundscapes Observer role, including classroom groups, families, and independent observers.

Scientists observe and take notes! Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Observers go outside on eclipse day to record what they hear, see, or feel during the 2023 and 2024 solar eclipses. Observers shared their notes from locations on, near, and off the eclipse path, helping scientists understand how people and animals responded to the sudden change in light and temperature.

ES Observer Requirements:

- Sign up as an ES Observer through the Eclipse Soundscapes website in order to receive role-specific training, reminders, and time-relevant guidance via email leading up to and immediately following the eclipse. (ES Observer Sign-up Form *Appendix 1*)
 - Beginning in 2024, role-specific email communications were used to provide structured, time-sensitive reminders and reinforce key preparation steps based on participant feedback from the 2023 annular eclipse.
- Complete the Apprentice Training, which introduces important eclipse information, project science goals, and eclipse safety information.
 - Severino, M., & Kline, T. (2025, November 24). ES Apprentice Role Curriculum: Solar Eclipses and Multi-Sensory Observing (Informal Education). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17703003>
- Observe & Take Field Notes during the eclipse
 - **TIME:** Observer at least 10 minutes before, during, and at least 10 minutes after the eclipse maximum during the solar eclipse.
 - **LOCATION:** record your observation [latitude & longitude \(DD format\)](#),
- After the eclipse, submit your Observations & location info via the online form

Structured Email Communication Timeline (2024)

Beginning with the 2024 total solar eclipse, ES implemented role-specific, time-sensitive email communications to support participant preparation and reduce confusion observed during the 2023 annular eclipse.

Observer emails were distributed in a scaffolded sequence, reinforcing key preparation steps, including:

Date	Topic	Purpose
2/18	Multisensory Observing	Reinforce training & encourage practice
2/25	Types of Observations	Clarify observational scope
3/3	Eclipse Maximum & Timing	Ensure correct observation window
3/10	Eclipse Safety	Reinforce safety protocol
3/17	Latitude & Longitude	Ensure correct coordinate reporting
4/1	Field Notes & Submission Form	Familiarize with submission
4/7	One-day Reminder	Pre-eclipse checklist
4/11	Submit Observations	Prompt timely data entry

This structured communication strategy supported just-in-time guidance and reinforced core participation protocols.

Training Webinars

Observers attended or watched a recording of a training webinar to learn:

- What changes in nature might you expect to observe during a solar eclipse
- Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Science Question Overview
- When & for how long to observe as an ES Observer
- Eclipse observation safety
- What to observe as an ES Observer
- Where to observe as an ES Observer
- Using Field Notes as an ES Observer
- How to submit your ES observations
- Eclipse Soundscapes Observers in the Classroom
- Eclipse Soundscapes Observers at Events

Recording of training webinar:

Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Role Training (March 18, 2024 Webinar)

<https://youtu.be/G633QOaYfnc>

Online Asynchronous Training

1. [How to Find and Format Location Latitude & Longitude for Submission](#)
2. [What is Eclipse Maximum](#)
3. [Annular and Total Solar Eclipse Safety](#)
4. [How might animals respond to Solar Eclipses](#)
5. [How to Observe with all of your senses](#)

1. How to find & format Latitude and Longitude (DD Format)

Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Observers and Data Collectors need to report their location using latitude and longitude. Latitude and longitude have different formats. ES uses Decimal Degrees (DD) format. Please record at least 5 decimal places. Below is some information and resources to help you find your latitude and longitude and make sure it is in the correct format.

Latitude and Longitude with Google Maps

Computer

1. On your computer, open [Google Maps](https://www.google.com/maps) (<https://www.google.com/maps>).
2. Right-click the place or area on the map.
 - This will open a pop-up window. You can find your latitude and longitude in decimal format at the top.
3. To copy the coordinates automatically, left click on the latitude and longitude

Reference: <https://support.google.com/maps/answer/18539?hl=en&co=GENIE.Platform%3DDesktop>

Android Phone or Tablet

1. On your Android phone or tablet, open the Google Maps application.
2. Touch and hold an area of the map that isn't labeled to drop a red pin.
3. In the search box, you can find the coordinates.

Reference:

<https://support.google.com/maps/answer/18539?hl=en&co=GENIE.Platform%3DAndroid&oco=1>

iPhone or iPad

1. On your iPhone or iPad, open the Google Maps application.
2. Touch and hold an area of the map that isn't labeled to drop a red pin.
3. At the bottom, tap Dropped pin to find the coordinates.

Reference:

<https://support.google.com/maps/answer/18539?hl=en&co=GENIE.Platform%3DiOS&oco=1>

Format Your Latitude and Longitude Coordinates

To format your coordinates so they work with the Observer and Data Collector online forms, use decimal degrees (DD) in the following format:

- Correct: 41.40338, 2.17403
- Incorrect: 41,40338, 2,17403

Tips:

- List your latitude coordinates before your longitude coordinates.
- Check that the first number in your latitude coordinate is between -90 and 90.
- Check that the first number in your longitude coordinate is between -180 and 180.

2. What is Eclipse Maximum

Eclipse maximum is the midpoint of an eclipse when the Moon blocks the most amount of Sun that it will block at that location. Eclipses take several hours, but eclipse maximum only happens for a few minutes. As an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer, you will need to observe for at least 10 minutes before eclipse maximum, during eclipse maximum, and at least 10 minutes after eclipse maximum. So, it's important to make sure you know what eclipse maximum is!

Two different solar eclipses will be happening in the US soon! There will be an annular eclipse on October 14, 2023 and a total solar eclipse on April 8, 2024. Because these are different kinds of solar eclipses, what you experience will be a little different.

If you took the ES Apprentice Training, this will be a review. If you did not take the Apprentice Training, it is a good idea to review this material before becoming an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer. The information is shared via video or text. You can choose which you prefer, or review both.

Video

Watch all 4:29 of this video for this lesson.

[What is Solar Eclipse Maximum?](#) By ARISA Lab

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y-aUK1CkuJU>

Reading

Annular Eclipse

Annular Solar Eclipse - Annularity, Copyright Tahna Zia 2020

Maximum Phase - Annularity

The maximum phase of the annular eclipse is annularity. Annularity is when the Moon blocks the center of the Sun from view. Eclipses can take hours, but annularity only lasts for a few minutes. During annularity, the Moon blocks the center of the Sun from view. This makes the Sun look like a “ring of fire.” In fact, annular eclipses are often called “Ring of Fire” eclipses. If you want to look at annularity, you **MUST** protect eyes with special eclipse glasses because all of the Sun’s powerful rays are not blocked.

Total Solar Eclipse

Total Solar Eclipse - Totality, Copyright: Miloslav Druckmüller & Peter Aniol 2006

Maximum Phase - Totality

The maximum phase of the total solar eclipse is totality. Totality is when the Moon blocks the entire Sun. Eclipses can take hours, but totality only lasts a few minutes. With the Moon blocking the entire Sun, you can see the Sun’s bright outer atmosphere called the corona, which is not usually visible. The Sun’s bright corona looks like soft flower petals surrounding the Moon. During Totality is the **ONLY** brief time that you can look at the Sun without special eclipse glasses because all of the Sun’s powerful rays are completely blocked.

Partial Solar Eclipse

Maximum Phase - Partial Eclipses

If you are near, but not in the path of annularity (for an annular eclipse) or near, but not in, the path of totality (for a total solar eclipse), you will experience a partial eclipse. If you are observing a partial eclipse, you won’t experience annularity or totality. Instead, you will need to find the eclipse maximum coverage in your area. That maximum is usually expressed as a percentage less than 100. (For example, you may experience a 75% eclipse or a 90% eclipse). During a partial eclipse, the moon will gradually cover some of the Sun until it reaches its maximum percentage in your area. Then it will gradually cover less of the Sun until it covers none of the Sun.

Solar Eclipse Safety

For both annular and total eclipses, remember to protect your eyes using eclipse glasses or a solar filter. Go to Eclipse Safety Resources for more eclipse safety information, and make sure to review the Apprentice Eclipse Safety Lesson, too. (Appendixes 3 & 4)

Vocabulary

annular eclipse – when the Moon passes directly in front of the Sun, but appears to be too small to completely cover the Sun

annularity – when the Moon blocks only the center of the Sun, leaving a ring of light visible during an annular eclipse. Annularity is the maximum phase of an annular solar eclipse.

corona – outer atmosphere of the Sun

maximum phase – the phase of an eclipse when the Moon is lined up with the Sun

total solar eclipse – when the Moon passes directly in front of the Sun completely blocking the Sun from view

totality – when the Moon blocks the entire Sun from view during a total solar eclipse. Totality is the maximum phase of a total solar eclipse.

Discussion / Notes

Write, draw, or verbally discuss the answers to the following:

- What is annularity?
- What is totality?

3. Annular and Total Solar Eclipse Safety

As an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer, you will be out in the field observing on eclipse day! Any time you are in the field, it's very important that safety is your highest priority. Please review the safety information below.

If you took the ES Apprentice Training, this will be a review. If you did not take the Apprentice Training, it is a good idea to review this material before becoming an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer. The information is shared via video or text. You can choose which you prefer, or review both.

Eye safety is very important during solar eclipses! Sunglasses WILL NOT protect your eyes. You also CANNOT look through a telescope or camera without a special solar filter. If you want to look at the Sun during a solar eclipse you MUST wear [special eclipse glasses](#)

(<https://eclipse.aas.org/resources/solar-filters>) or use a [special eclipse viewer](https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/optics-filters) (<https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/optics-filters>). There is one eclipse safety difference between the total solar eclipse and all the other solar eclipse types. Please keep reading to learn the difference and stay safe!

Reading 1

Annular Eclipse Safety (Oct 14, 2023)

You CANNOT look at the sun without eclipse glasses or a solar filter during an annular solar eclipse, such as the one on October 14, 2023. There is NO time when it is safe to look directly at the Sun without wearing eclipse glasses or using a special solar filter.

You must make sure you have official eclipse glasses or the correct solar filter. Please visit the [American Astronomical Society website](https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety) (<https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>) for up-to-date and accurate information on suppliers of safe eclipse glasses and filters.

Video 1

Watch 1:13-1:44 of this video for this lesson.

[What Is an Annular Eclipse?](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sNBbMWkSlh4) By NASA Goddard
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sNBbMWkSlh4>

Reading 2

Total Solar Eclipse Safety (April 8, 2024)

A total solar eclipse has 5 phases. There is ONLY one phase when you can remove your eclipse glasses briefly while looking at the Sun. During the maximum phase of a total solar eclipse you can take off your eclipse glasses briefly because the entire Sun is blocked from view. The maximum phase is called totality. Totality is when the Moon entirely blocks the Sun's bright surface. This happens for only a few minutes during a total solar eclipse. ([Eclipse Safety information](https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety) - <https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>)

Video 2

Watch 2:32-4:20 of this video for this lesson.

[Solar Eclipse 101](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cxrLRbkOwKs) By Smithsonian
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cxrLRbkOwKs>

Reading 3

Partial Solar Eclipse Safety

If you are NOT on the eclipse path on October 14, 2023 or April 8, 2024 you will experience a partial eclipse. There is NO time when it is safe to look directly at the Sun without wearing [eclipse glasses](#) or a [solar filter](#) during a partial solar eclipse (<https://eclipse.aas.org/resources/solar-filters>) . You CANNOT look at the sun without eclipse glasses or a solar filter.

You must make sure you have official eclipse glasses or the correct solar filter. Please visit the [American Astronomical Society website](#) for up-to-date and accurate information on suppliers of safe eclipse glasses and filters. (<https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>)

Vocabulary

annular eclipse – when the Moon passes directly in front of the Sun, but appears to be too small to completely block the Sun

maximum phase – the phase of an eclipse when the Moon is lined up with the Sun

partial solar eclipse – when the Moon passes in front of the Sun off-center and does not block the surface

solar filter – a filter added on to a camera or telescope that blocks out most of the Sun’s light to allow the user to look at the Sun

total solar eclipse – when the Moon passes directly in front of the Sun completely blocking the Sun from view

Discussion / Notes

Write, draw, or verbally discuss the answers to the following:

- During which phase of a total solar eclipse is it ok to take off your eclipse glasses?
- Is it ever safe to take off your eclipse glasses during an annular eclipse?
- Is it ever safe to take off your eclipse glasses during a partial solar eclipse?
- Who will experience a partial eclipse on October 14, 2023 and April 8, 2024?

Bonus Activity

Make a Pinhole Projector

- [How to Make a Pinhole Camera \(NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology\)](https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/edu/learn/project/how-to-make-a-pinhole-camera/) - <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/edu/learn/project/how-to-make-a-pinhole-camera/>

- [How to make a pinhole projector to view the solar eclipse \(CNET\)](https://www.cnet.com/science/how-to-make-a-pinhole-projector-to-view-the-eclipse/) - <https://www.cnet.com/science/how-to-make-a-pinhole-projector-to-view-the-eclipse/>
- [Projection: Pinhole & Optical \(American Astronomical Society\)](https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/projection) <https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/projection>

4. How might animals respond to Solar Eclipses

As an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer, you might be wondering what different things you might hear or see on eclipse day. That is exactly what Eclipse Soundscapes wants to document! Below you will learn about some of the animal reactions that other people have observed during past solar eclipses.

If you took the ES Apprentice Training, this will be a review. If you did not take the Apprentice Training, it is a good idea to review this material before becoming an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer. The information is shared via video or text. You can choose which you prefer, or review both.

Reading

Nature has its own rhythm and motion. Animals make all kinds of noises like chirping and buzzing and also make all kinds of audible movements through their environment. What happens during a solar eclipse? As the Moon blocks out the Sun and the Earth becomes darker and cooler, the animal kingdom reacts. According to researchers, during the maximum phase, birds stop singing and hide in their nests. Bees get louder. They start to buzz loudly and fly in and out of their hives. On farms, chickens and cows start to walk back to the barn because they think it is nighttime. And, interestingly, a solar eclipse seems to wake up nocturnal animals even though it is the middle of the day! Bats and owls become more alert and start to feed. The maximum phase of a solar eclipse only lasts for a few minutes. Almost as quickly as it came, the Sun starts to reappear and daylight returns. The animals become a bit confused. But as the Sun comes back, suddenly there is an explosion of sound.

Video

Watch all 1:16 of this video for this lesson.

[What Do Animals Do During a Solar Eclipse](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mpF5GGc3lYs) By CNN 10
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mpF5GGc3lYs>

Vocabulary

nocturnal animals – animals who sleep during the day and are active at night

Discussion / Notes

Write, draw, or verbally discuss the answers to the following questions:

- How does a solar eclipse affect animals? Why does this happen?

5. How to Observe with all of your senses

As an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer, and as a scientist, it is important to observe with all of the senses available to you. On eclipse day, make sure to put away your phone and other electronic devices while you observe (unless you are using your device to take notes). Concentrate on each sense available to you. This will be different for everyone.

If you took the ES Apprentice Training, this will be a review. If you did not take the Apprentice Training, it is a good idea to review this material before becoming an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer. The information is shared via video or text. You can choose which you prefer, or review both.

Reading

What do you hear? What do you see? What do you feel? Take notes so you don't forget. If you heard insects, do you know what kind? If you saw an animal, do you know what kind? Write down all of the details so you have them for later!

Eclipse Soundscape Observers should pay special attention to changes from right before eclipse maximum to during eclipse maximum. Did you hear animal sounds increase or decrease? Did it get hotter or colder? Did you notice any insect or animal behavior changes? Eclipse Soundscapes Observers should also write the day and time that they started and stopped observing and information about the location. Location information includes city, suburb, or rural and a description of the surroundings – are you near a river or lake? In a field? In a park? etc.

Video

Watch all 1:39 of this video for this lesson.

[Observing with ALL Senses](https://youtu.be/p-TMadYD-nc) By ARISA Lab
<https://youtu.be/p-TMadYD-nc>

Observer Practice

Observe in a multi-sensory way right now by following these steps:

Use a notebook

Write date and start time

Write location info: Latitude and longitude?
City, suburb, or rural location? Describe: park, field, near river, etc?

Quietly observe with all of your senses

Write down your observation stop time and your observations

Vocabulary

rural – a place outside a town or city with not many people, countryside.

Discuss

After you practice observing, talk about your observations with a friend.

Even if you both observed at the same time and in the same location, you might have different observations. This is because everyone notices different things. That is why we need everyone's help with Eclipse Soundscapes! Different people notice different things and it is all important scientific information!

Eclipse Day Instructions

Observe on Eclipse Day!

Following the instructions below, most participants observed for 20–30 minutes total (10 minutes before eclipse maximum, during maximum, and 10 minutes after). Many also extended their observations longer to capture more changes in nature.

Observe for at least 10 minutes before eclipse maximum, during eclipse maximum, and for at least 10 minutes after eclipse maximum.
(You should set aside at least 20-30 minutes for eclipse observation. And longer is of course appreciated!)

Take notes while you observe!

Where: Latitude & Longitude (DD format)

When: Observation Start & Stop Time

Observe: Did you hear or see any changes in animal behavior during eclipse maximum?

Use *Observer field notes* form to take notes on eclipse day! (Appendix 5 [Eng], Appendix 6 [Spanish])

Submit your observations on the Eclipse Soundscapes website via the online form.

Resources

Observer Form Preview

Online survey questions preview were shared with participants in PDF format.

ES Observer Role Survey Preview - Appendix 2

Safety

Eclipse Safety handouts were developed by NASA, NOAA, AAS, and NSF and shared with all Observers on the ES website in PDF format on every Observer training page.

How to Safely View the April 8, 2024, Total Solar Eclipse [ENGLISH] - Appendix 3

How to Safely View the April 8, 2024, Total Solar Eclipse [SPANISH] - Appendix 4

Observer Field Notes

Observers used printable Field Notes papers provided in English and Spanish in PDF and Google Doc formats in 2023 and 2024) to record:

- Location (latitude & longitude)
- Observation start and stop times
- Sensory details (what they heard, saw, and felt)

To help take effective notes, we recommend using the Eclipse Soundscapes Field Notes handout on Eclipse day.

Field Notes paper (PDF) [English] - Appendix 5

Field Notes paper (PDF) [Spanish] - Appendix 6

Data Transparency Note

The guidance in this manual reflects the training materials provided to ES Observers prior to data submission. Observation data submitted through project forms were deidentified prior to public release. Personal identifiers, certificate-related information, and optional participation tracking fields were removed from publicly archived datasets.

Certificate and SciStarter Credit

Certificate of Completion

Volunteer scientists who participated in Eclipse Soundscapes as ES Observers received an ES Observer Certificate of Completion after submitting their observation form. In 2023, the form was administered through Alchemer, and in 2024 through Qualtrics. In both years, participants could access the forms via the Eclipse Soundscapes website.

At the beginning of the observation form, participants indicated whether they were 13 years of age or older or under 13 years of age. Certificate delivery options were determined by this selection.

Participants who indicated they were 13 years of age or older were given two options after submission:

- View and print the certificate directly from the screen
- Enter their name and email address to receive a personalized certificate via email

Participants who indicated they were under 13 years of age were not given the option to enter a name or email address. Instead, they were provided a printable certificate without name personalization. A supervising adult could manually add the participant's name after printing. This approach ensured compliance with youth privacy protections while supporting classroom, family, and group-based participation.

All ES Observer certificates were designed to be accessible, including compatibility with screen readers. The certificate workflow reflects Eclipse Soundscapes' commitment to Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles by providing multiple means of representation and expression, flexible access pathways, and privacy-conscious participation options. Participants could access certificates digitally or in print, with or without personalization.

Certificate-related fields, including names and email addresses used for optional personalization, were not included in the publicly released datasets archived on Zenodo.

All submission forms were designed and tested for accessibility, including the use of screen reader-compatible question formats, clear labeling, logical tab order, and minimal reliance on

visual formatting. Question structures were intentionally selected to ensure compatibility across assistive technologies and to reduce cognitive load.

SciStarter Affiliate Participation and Credit

The Eclipse Soundscapes project partnered with SciStarter to support coordinated participation tracking and volunteer scientist recognition. (Reference: <https://scistarter.org>)

Through the SciStarter Affiliate Program, the ES Observer role was listed as an official SciStarter activity and highlighted as an eclipse engagement opportunity. Participation credit could be recorded on a volunteer scientist's SciStarter Dashboard, typically within approximately 24 hours of verified form submission.

To receive SciStarter credit, participants who indicated they were 13 years of age or older were given the option, at the end of the submission form, to enter the email address associated with their SciStarter account. This email address was used solely to transmit participation credit and connect the submission to the participant's SciStarter Dashboard.

Participants under 13 years of age were not provided the option to enter an email address for SciStarter credit, ensuring that contact information from children under 13 was not collected.

Participation credit through SciStarter was optional and did not affect completion of the ES Observer role. Email addresses provided for SciStarter credit were not included in the publicly released observation datasets archived on Zenodo.

Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Sign Up

Signing up does not obligate you to participate. By signing up via this form you agree to receive emails updating you on important steps and deadlines associated with being an ES Observer for the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse. You may opt-out from receiving emails at any time after sign-up by contacting Outreach@ArisaLab.org

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. How did you hear about the Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Role? *

Mark only one oval.

- Google Search
- Texas Master Naturalists
- NASA Website
- SciStarter
- National Federation of the Blind
- friend or family
- library
- school
- Other:

3. **What is your State?** (Please use standard two-letter abbreviations for US states or territories) *

Appendix 1

4. What is your zip code? *

5. Why are you interested in being an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer?

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

English ▾

Introduction

Eclipse Soundscapes Observation Submission

Thank you for participating in the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Project as an Observer!

This questionnaire has multiple parts:

1. A section to collect information about your **Observation Location**.
2. A section to collect information about your **Eclipse Observations**.
3. Access to the **Observer Role Completion Certificate**.
4. A **Reflection Survey** to evaluate your experience with ES as an Observer.

Your participation is entirely voluntary. Your responses to the survey will be separated from your observation submission to maintain confidentiality. Results from the survey will be reported in aggregate to evaluate the program's impact and support research efforts in determining how projects like this affect people's science identity.

All submitted observations and observation location information will be freely and publicly available with an attribution thanking volunteers for their contribution. Please see the "[Open Data Policy](#)" page on the EclipseSoundscapes.org website for more information about this policy and where ES data will be stored.

The entire process is expected to take 15-30 minutes. If you have any questions, feel free to contact David Bauer (dbauer@themarkusa.com) or Adrienne Celaya (acelaya@themarkusa.com).

How old are you?

- I am 12 years old or younger.
- I am 13 years old or older.

What is your 5-digit zip code?

This might be different from the zip code where you completed the observation. This information is shared with NASA Science Activation so that they can better understand where people are getting involved with the projects that they support. If you do not know your zip code, or if you live outside of the United States, please enter 99999.

Privacy Policy

I understand that any data that I provide will be used for the stated purposes: first, to collect information about my observation location and observations; second, to generate my certificate; and third, to help evaluate how participatory science influenced my science identity.

I understand that The Eclipse Soundscapes project is run by ARISA Lab, but a different organization called The Mark USA has been hired to collect the data that I will provide here. The Mark USA will not share any identifiable information that I provide (for example, my name and email address) with ARISA Lab. Also, I understand that The Mark USA will not use my information for any purposes beyond those stated here and will not share or sell my contact information or other data for any reason, unless obligated by law.

I understand that my IP address and geo-location data will not be automatically recorded.

I understand that participants under the age of 13 will not be asked to provide identifiable information.

I consent to providing information for the purposes of this study. I understand that I can opt out at any time by closing the tab or window.

LOCATION

What is the location of your observation? Please enter your location using your device's location or type in latitude and longitude in decimal degrees.

Latitude values will range from -90 to 90. Longitude values will range from -180 to 180. Both can include up to 10 digits after the decimal point.

- Example latitude values: 41.40338, -50.89823810, 2.255
- Example longitude values: -162.999987, 30.8753, 170.042

Latitude

Longitude

What is the location of your observation? Please enter your location by typing in the latitude and longitude (in decimal degrees) provided by the adult helping you.

Latitude values will range from -90 to 90. Longitude values will range from -180 to 180. Both can include up to 10 digits after the decimal point.

- Example latitude values: 41.40338, -50.89823810, 2.255
- Example longitude values: -162.999987, 30.8753, 170.042
- If there is not an adult or person over 18 helping you, please do not provide location information.

Latitude

Longitude

Please select the option that describes your outside observation location:

- Urban / City
- Suburban
- Rural / Countryside

Please select additional descriptions that describe your outside observation location: Choose all that apply.

- Park
- Forest
- Field or pasture
- Desert
- Beach
- Riverfront
- Lakefront
- Mountain area
- Hiking or Biking trail
- Zoo
- Farm
- National Park, please specify:
- National or State Forest, please specify:
- Other, please specify:

How many other people are around you?

- None (i'm alone)
- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11-20
- 21-50
- More than 50

Do you have additional information to share about your location? (For example, near a major road? Near a power generator or power supply station? Near particular animals/insects nesting/habitat? etc) Details and info always help!

Qualtrics Survey Software

Observation Start Time:

What time did you begin your observations? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09.

Observation Stop Time:

What time are you stopping your observations? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09.

Please select your time zone:

- Eastern Time Zone
- Central Time Zone
- Mountain Time Zone
- Pacific Time Zone
- Alaska Time Zone
- Hawaii-Aleutian Time Zone

OBSERVATIONS_SOUND

Directions: Please answer the following questions to help you think about and record information you observed.

Every person is in a different location, observes different things, and has different senses available to them. You might not have answers for every observation question and that is completely expected and okay. All observations support research on how solar eclipses affect the wildlife and the environment!

Do you have sound observations to report?

- Yes
- No

Please indicate whether you heard a sound from the items listed below. "Yes" means you heard the item in your area. "No" means you did not hear the item in your area. You may also choose "I don't know" if you cannot decide whether or not you heard the item in your area.

We would like to know what you heard and if you heard any behavior changes during the eclipse maximum as compared to right before and right after the eclipse maximum.

Did you hear insects? (crickets, cicadas, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which insects did you hear? (Please list)

Did you hear any behavior changes in insects? (Please explain)

Did you hear birds? (crows, sparrows, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which birds did you hear? (Please list)

Did you hear any behavior changes in birds? (Please explain)

Did you hear amphibians? (toads, frogs, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which amphibians did you hear? (Please list)

Did you hear any behavior changes in amphibians? (Please explain)

Did you hear mammals? (squirrels, dogs, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which mammals did you hear? (Please list)

**Did you hear any behavior changes in mammals?
(Please explain)**

Did you hear reptiles? (lizards, anoles, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which reptiles did you hear? (Please list)

Did you hear any behavior changes in reptiles? (Please explain)

Did you hear humans?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Did you hear any behavior changes in humans? (Please explain)

Did you hear vehicles? (cars, boats, tractors, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which vehicles did you hear? (Please list)

Did you hear any behavior changes in vehicles? (Please explain)

Please share any additional observations about the sound differences or similarities that you heard during the eclipse maximum as compared to right before and right after the eclipse maximum.

OBSERVATIONS_VISUAL

Do you have visual observations to report?

- Yes
- No

Please indicate whether you saw a sight from the items listed below. "Yes" means you saw the item in your area. "No" means you did not see the item in your area. You may also choose "I don't know" if you cannot decide whether or not you saw the item in your area.

We would like to know what you saw and if you saw any behavior changes during the eclipse maximum as

compared to right before and right after the eclipse maximum.

Did you see insects? (crickets, cicadas, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which insects did you see? (Please list)

Did you see any behavior changes in insects? (Please explain)

Did you see birds? (crows, sparrows, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which birds did you see? (Please list)

Did you see any behavior changes in birds? (Please explain)

Did you see amphibians? (toads, frogs, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which amphibians did you see? (Please list)

Did you see any behavior changes in amphibians? (Please explain)

Did you see mammals? (squirrels, dogs, etc.)

- Yes

Appendix 2- ES Observer Role Submission form Preview

- No
- I don't know

Which mammals did you see? (Please list)

**Did you see any behavior changes in mammals?
(Please explain)**

Did you see reptiles? (lizards, anoles, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which reptiles did you see? (Please list)

Did you see any behavior changes in reptiles? (Please explain)

Did you see humans?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Did you see any behavior changes in humans? (Please explain)

Did you see vehicles? (cars, boats, tractors, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Which vehicles did you see? (Please list)

Did you see any behavior changes in vehicles? (Please explain)

Please share any additional observations about the visual differences or similarities that you saw during the eclipse maximum as compared to right before and right after the eclipse maximum.

OBSERVATIONS_OTHER

What other sensory observations can you share about the differences or similarities that you experienced during eclipse maximum as compared to right before and right after eclipse maximum?

Touch / Feel:

Nose / Smell:

Are there any other observations you'd like to share?

EXPERIENCE

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements regarding your experience of the eclipse.

	Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neutral	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
I experienced the passage of time differently.	<input type="radio"/>						
I had the sense of being connected to everything.	<input type="radio"/>						
I experienced something greater than myself.	<input type="radio"/>						
I felt challenged to understand the experience.	<input type="radio"/>						

BEFORE being an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer, which of the following senses did you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply.

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound
- Touch / Feel
- Nose / Smell
- Tongue / Taste

Now, AFTER being an Eclipse Soundscapes Observer, which of the following senses did you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply.

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound
- Touch / Feel
- Nose / Smell
- Tongue / Taste

Observer Certificate of Completion and SciStarter Credit

This section asks for information to email your certificate of completion, or to provide a link to print or save the certificate. You can also earn SciStarter credit if you have a SciStarter account.

Observer Certificate of Completion

Would you like your SciStarter account to be credited for your participation?

- Yes
 No

Please enter the email address associated with your SciStarter account.

Would you like the certificate emailed to you?

- Yes
 No

What is the email address you would like your certificate to be sent to? Please type it below.

The evaluation team would like to interview some ES Project participants to learn more about their experiences. Do we have your permission to contact you in the future to request an interview?

- Yes
- No, thank you

You can access the certificate by clicking the link below;

it will open in a new browser window or tab. Then you can print or save the certificate from your browser. There are places for you to add your name and date of completion.

[Click here to print or save the certificate!](#) [English version]

[Click here to print or save the certificate!](#) [Spanish version]

After printing or saving your certificate, please click 'Next' to begin the Reflection Survey.

How to Safely View the April 8, 2024, TOTAL SOLAR ECLIPSE

A solar eclipse occurs when the Moon blocks any part of the Sun. On Monday, April 8, 2024, a solar eclipse will be visible in North and Central America, as well as parts of Europe and South America. All 50 U.S. states (excluding most of Alaska) will have a chance to see at least a partial solar eclipse. In a narrow track across Mexico, the U.S. from Texas to Maine, and Canada from Ontario to Newfoundland, the Moon will completely cover the Sun's bright face, producing a spectacular total solar eclipse.

A total solar eclipse is about as bright as a full Moon — and just as safe to look at. But the Sun at any other time is dangerously bright. View it only through special-purpose solar filters that comply with the transmittance requirements of the ISO 12312-2 international standard for filters for direct solar viewing.

Protect Your Eyes

- Looking directly at the Sun without proper eye protection is unsafe EXCEPT during the brief total eclipse phase (“totality”). This happens ONLY within the narrow path of totality. At all other times, it is safe to look directly at the Sun ONLY through special-purpose solar filters, such as “eclipse glasses,” that comply with the transmittance requirements of the ISO 12312-2 international standard. Ordinary sunglasses, even very dark ones, are not safe for looking at the Sun.
- If you are inside the path of totality on April 8, 2024, remove your solar filter ONLY when the Moon completely covers the Sun’s bright face. As soon as the Sun begins to reappear, replace your solar filter to look at the remaining partial phases.
- Outside the path of totality, there is NO TIME when it is safe to look directly at the Sun without using a solar filter that complies with the transmittance requirements of the ISO 12312-2 international standard.

Instructions for the Safe Use of Solar Filters and Viewers

- Always inspect your solar filter before use; if scratched, punctured, torn, or otherwise damaged, discard it. Read and follow any instructions printed on or packaged with the filter.
- Always supervise children using solar filters.
- If you normally wear eyeglasses, keep them on. Put your eclipse glasses on over them or hold your handheld viewer in front of them.
- Stand still and cover your eyes with your eclipse glasses or solar viewer before looking at the bright Sun. After looking at the Sun, turn away and remove your filter – do not remove it while looking at the Sun.
- Do not look at the uneclipsed or partially eclipsed Sun through an unfiltered camera, telescope, binoculars, or other optical device. Do not do so even while wearing eclipse glasses or using a handheld solar viewer in front of your eyes – the concentrated solar rays could damage the filter and enter your eyes, causing serious injury.
- Solar filters must be securely attached to the front of any telescope, binoculars, or camera lens. Seek expert advice from an astronomer before using a solar filter with a camera, telescope, binoculars, or any other optical device.

What If You Don't Have a Safe Solar Filter or Viewer?

Another method for safe viewing of the partially eclipsed Sun is indirectly via pinhole projection. For example, with your back to the Sun, cross the outstretched, slightly open fingers of one hand over the outstretched, slightly open fingers of the other, creating a waffle pattern. In your hands' shadow on the ground, the spaces between your fingers will show the Sun as crescents.

A solar eclipse is one of nature's grandest spectacles. By following these simple rules, you can safely enjoy the view and be rewarded with memories to last a lifetime. For more information about eye safety and the eclipse, visit <https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>.

This safety information has been endorsed by the American Astronomical Society, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, the U.S. National Science Foundation, the American Academy of Ophthalmology, the American Academy of Optometry, and the American Medical Association.

Cómo ver de forma segura el **ECLIPSE SOLAR TOTAL** del 8 de abril de 2024

Un eclipse solar ocurre cuando la Luna bloquea cualquier parte del Sol. El lunes 8 de abril de 2024, un eclipse solar será visible en América del Norte y Central, así como en partes de Europa y América del Sur. Los 50 estados de Estados Unidos (excluyendo la mayor parte de Alaska) tendrán la oportunidad de ver al menos un eclipse solar parcial. En un estrecho recorrido a través de México, Estados Unidos desde Texas hasta Maine y Canadá desde Ontario hasta Terranova, la Luna cubrirá completamente la cara brillante del Sol, produciendo un espectacular eclipse solar total.

Un eclipse solar total es tan brillante como una luna llena, e igual de seguro de observar. Pero en cualquier otro momento, el Sol es peligrosamente brillante. Míralo solo a través de filtros solares especiales para ese propósito que cumplan con los requisitos de transmisión de la norma internacional ISO 12312-2 para filtros de observación directa del Sol.

Protege tus ojos

- Mirar directamente al Sol sin la protección ocular adecuada no es seguro, EXCEPTO durante la breve fase del eclipse total (la "totalidad"). Esto ocurre SOLO dentro del estrecho camino de la totalidad. En cualquier otro momento, SOLO es seguro mirar directamente al Sol a través de filtros solares especiales para ese propósito, como los "anteojos para eclipses", que cumplen con los requisitos de transmisión de la norma internacional ISO 12312-2. Las gafas de sol comunes, incluso las muy oscuras, no son seguras para mirar el Sol.
- Si estás dentro del camino de la totalidad el 8 de abril de 2024, puedes quitarte el filtro solar SOLO cuando la Luna cubra completamente la cara brillante del Sol. Tan pronto como el Sol comience a reaparecer, vuelve a colocarte el filtro solar para ver las fases parciales restantes.
- Fuera de la trayectoria de la totalidad, NO HAY NINGÚN MOMENTO en el que sea seguro mirar directamente al Sol sin usar un filtro solar que cumpla con los requisitos de transmisión de la norma internacional ISO 12312-2.

Instrucciones para el uso seguro de filtros y visores solares

- Examina siempre tu filtro solar antes de usarlo; no lo uses si está rayado, perforado, rasgado o dañado. Lee y sigue las instrucciones que vienen impresas o empaquetadas con el filtro.
- Siempre debes supervisar a los niños cuando utilicen filtros solares.
- Si normalmente usas anteojos, mantenlos puestos. Ponte tus anteojos para eclipses sobre ellos o sostén tu visor manual frente a ellos.
- No te muevas y cúbrete los ojos con tus anteojos para eclipses o tu visor solar antes de mirar hacia el Sol brillante. Después de mirar al Sol, date vuelta en dirección opuesta al Sol y quítate el filtro; no te lo quites mientras estás mirando al Sol.
- No mires al Sol sin eclipsar o parcialmente eclipsado a través de una cámara, telescopio, binoculares u otro dispositivo óptico que no tenga filtro. No lo hagas incluso mientras usas anteojos para eclipses o mientras tienes un visor solar manual frente a los ojos: los rayos solares concentrados podrían dañar el filtro y entrar en tus ojos, causando lesiones graves.
- Los filtros solares deben estar sujetos de forma segura a la parte frontal de cualquier telescopio, binoculares o la lente de una cámara. Busca el consejo experto de un astrónomo antes de usar un filtro solar con una cámara, telescopio, binoculares o cualquier otro dispositivo óptico.

¿Qué pasa si no tienes un filtro o visor solar seguro?

Otro método para la observación segura del Sol eclipsado parcialmente es de forma indirecta mediante la proyección estenopeica (con agujero). Por ejemplo, mientras das la espalda al Sol, cruza los dedos extendidos y ligeramente abiertos de una mano sobre los dedos extendidos y ligeramente abiertos de la otra, creando un patrón de rejilla, como un *waffle*. A la sombra de tus manos en el suelo, los espacios entre tus dedos mostrarán el Sol como medias lunas.

Un eclipse solar es uno de los espectáculos más grandiosos de la naturaleza. Al seguir estas reglas sencillas, puedes disfrutar de la vista de forma segura y ser recompensado con recuerdos para toda la vida. Para obtener más información sobre la seguridad ocular y el eclipse, visita la página (en inglés): <https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>.

Esta información de seguridad ha sido respaldada por la Sociedad Astronómica Estadounidense, la Administración Nacional de Aeronáutica y el Espacio, la Administración Nacional Oceánica y Atmosférica, la Fundación Nacional para las Ciencias de Estados Unidos, la Academia Estadounidense de Oftalmología, la Academia Estadounidense de Optometría y la Asociación Médica Estadounidense.

Eclipse Soundscapes Observer- Field Notes

How do solar eclipses affect animals & insects?

Date: _____ Location: _____

Latitude & Longitude (DD) _____

Location Type: (urban / suburban / country) _____

Location Description: (forest, park, lakefront, etc) _____

How many people are nearby? _____

← Eclipse Maximum

Weather: _____

Start Time: _____

Observation Start Time: _____ Observation Stop Time: _____

(For 10+ minutes) Before Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles

During Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
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Eclipse Soundscapes Observer- Field Notes

How do solar eclipses affect animals & insects?

Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles
---------	----------	-----------------

(For 10+ minutes) After Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles

Additional Observations / Notes:

Submit your observations so they can be included in the Eclipse Soundscapes Project & receive an Observer Certificate!
EclipseSoundscapes.org/Observer

Appendix 6

Observador de Eclipse Soundscapes - Notas de campo

¿Cómo afectan los eclipses solares a los animales y los insectos?

Fecha: _____ Ubicación: _____

Latitud y Longitud (DD) _____

Tipo de ubicación: (urbana/suburbana/rural) _____

Descripción de la ubicación: (parque, frente a un lago, etc.) _____

¿Cuántas personas hay cerca? _____

Hora de inicio del
máximo del eclipse: _____

Clima: _____

Hora de inicio de la observación: _____ Hora de fin de la observación: _____

(Para más de 10 minutos) Antes del máximo del eclipse (oír/ver/tocar) -

¿Especie? ¿Comportamiento?

Insectos	Aves	Anfibios
Mamíferos	Reptiles	Gente/vehículos

Durante el máximo del eclipse (oír/ver/tocar) - ¿Especie? ¿Comportamiento?

Insectos	Aves	Anfibios
----------	------	----------

Appendix 6

Observador de Eclipse Soundscapes - Notas de campo ¿Cómo afectan los eclipses solares a los animales y los insectos?

Mamíferos	Reptiles	Gente/vehículos
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(Para más de 10 minutos) Después del máximo del eclipse (oír/ver/tocar) -
¿Especie? ¿Comportamiento?

Insectos	Aves	Anfibios
Mamíferos	Reptiles	Gente/vehículos

Otras observaciones/Notas:

¡**Envíe sus observaciones** para que puedan incluirse en el Proyecto Eclipse Soundscapes y reciba un Certificado de Observador!
EclipseSoundscapes.org/Observer

EclipseSoundscapes.org is supported by NASA award No. 80NSSC21M0008

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT

(NAME)

has successfully completed the Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Role.

(DATE)

Henry Winter

Dr. Henry "Trae" Winter, Chief Scientist

MaryKay Severino

MaryKay Severino, Education Director

Partner

Eclipse Soundscapes is supported by
NASA Grant # 80NSSC21M0008

CERTIFICADO DE FINALIZACIÓN

Esto certifica que

(NOMBRE)

ha completado con éxito el rol de observador de Eclipse Soundscapes.

(FECHA)

Henry Winter

Dr. Henry "Trae" Winter, Chief Scientist

MaryKay Severino

MaryKay Severino, Education Director

Partner

Eclipse Soundscapes is supported by
NASA Grant # 80NSSC21M0008